

THE RELATIONSHIP OF JOB SATISFACTION, FLEXIBLE WORK ARRANGEMENTS AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE: A CASE STUDY OF EMPLOYEES IN SEVERAL PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES IN KLANG VALLEY, MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT

Job satisfaction (JS) is very crucial towards employee's performance (EP). Past studies have answered that employee performance is highly affected by flexible working arrangements (FWAs) and job satisfaction. Flexible working arrangements (FWAs) at the workplace has become everyone's wishes to work at home without having to go through the hassle on the road such as heavy traffic, toll, parking and petrol. This FWAs also will intensification the employee's performance to the utmost. Thus, job satisfaction will increase employee morale and loyalty, increases self-belonging towards an organization and longer-term employee performance. Hence, at the same time, FWAs had positively impacted the employee's level of job satisfaction. The respondents of the study are among the employees of several private universities in Klang Valley. Returned respondents were only 188. Descriptive statistics were utilised to describe the demographic profile of respondents and hierarchical Multi Linear Regression analysis has been used for estimating the relationship among the variables. Therefore, given the employees the FWAs will improve employees performance, that is significant to self-confident and indirectly impacted their quality of work, job satisfaction, and loyal to the organization. Hence, this paper is particularly interested in the investigation on the relationship between job satisfaction, flexible working arrangement and employee performance of several private universities in Klang Valley. The results of the study indicate that job satisfaction has a significant influence towards FWAs with $B=.470$, $t=-13.150$ and JS $B=.470$, $t=5.672$, and FWAs $B=1.077$, $t=8.807$ both have a significant influence on EP respectively.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, employee's performance, flexible working arrangements

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction and employee's performance are very much related. Every scholar has debated about job satisfaction and employee performance in which contribute to the organizational performance (Khan, Nawaz, Aleem, & Hamed, 2012). Despite having job satisfaction and employee's performance, one of the variables that have been impacted the performance of employees is flexible working arrangement (FWAs). Scholar (Chen, 2015) have been further debated on flexible working arrangement that consist of flexi-time, compressed workweek, working from home, job sharing, and reduced work hours that contribute to job satisfaction and employee's performance.

Therefore, further exploration towards flexible working arrangements, job satisfaction and employee performance at several private universities in Klang Valley is needed. The significant

of study will contribute to government, private universities, group link companies (GLCs) and other private company to consider such good practice in making sure the employees perform better and contribute to the organization (Pushpakumari, 2008). Excel in their performance and having a good job satisfaction (Management, 2008).

Thus, having such quality of life (QOL) and quality of work (QOW) also will improve their efficiency, more productive and effective to the organization. The organization can increase the morale of the employee, gain their loyalty, enhance basic physical fitness, increase production, increase savings, and profit-making opportunities (Lu, 2011). Hence, FWAs plays an important role in improving employee performance. According to Ortega (2009), Lee & Devoe (2012) having flexible working arrangements will reduce the employees major misconduct in an organization. Hyman & Summers (2004), Igarria & Guimaraes (1999), Baltes, Briggs, Huff, Wright, & Neuman (1999) said that flexible working arrangements had positively impacted employees level of job satisfaction.

Therefore, given the employees, FWAs will improve their efficiency, performance that is significant towards self-confident that impacted on their quality of work, and job satisfaction (Pruchno, Litchfield, & Fried, 2000). Thus, this paper is particularly interested in examining the relationship between job satisfaction (JS), flexible working arrangement (FWAs), and employee's performance (EP) of employees in several private universities in Klang Valley.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between job satisfaction, flexible working arrangement and employee's performance at several private universities in Klang Valley. There is still a lack of study to further investigate the relationship between FWAs, JS and EP. The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

- a. To identify the significant influence of Job Satisfaction towards Flexible Working Arrangements.
- b. To identify the significant influence of Flexible Working Arrangements (FWAs) towards Employee Performance.
- c. To determine the significant influence of Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- a) Does Job Satisfaction have significant influence towards Flexible Working Arrangement?
- b) Does Flexible Working Arrangement have a significant influence on Employee Performance?
- c) Does Job Satisfaction have a significant influence on Employee Performance?

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

The independent variables for this study are job satisfaction (JS), flexible working arrangement (FWAs) while the dependent variable is employee performance (EP). Job satisfaction was adopted from (Spector, 1997), employee performance (Koopmans et al., 2012) and flexible work arrangement from the Australian Government, Workplace Gender Equality Agency.

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTION AND FLEXIBLE WORKING ARRANGEMENTS

Spector, (1997) recognized that Job Satisfaction is where the individuals like their jobs and some love their work and find it meaningful of their life and while others hate to work so they do because they must (Spector, 1997). Indirectly, with such satisfaction can increase employee morale and loyalty, increases self-belonging towards an organization and longer-term employee performance (Scandura & Lankau, 1997). Hyman & Summers (2004), Igbaria & Guimaraes (1999), Baltes, Briggs, Huff, Wright, & Neuman (1999) said that flexible working arrangements had positively impacted employees level of job satisfaction. Therefore, given the employees of FWAs will increase their performance, efficiency that is significant with self-confident impacted on the quality of work, loyalty to the organization and having a job satisfaction (Pruchno et al., 2000).

Based on that notion, the researcher proposed that there is a significant relationship between Job Satisfaction and Flexible Working Arrangement.

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FLEXIBLE WORKING ARRANGEMENTS AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

Employee performance (EP) is about aligning the organisation's objective, skills and competencies of the existing employees so that the organisation will achieve the desired goals (Odembo, 2013). Thus, having a staff who is committed and happy to their job will definitely have job satisfaction and perform up to the standard of expectations (Shaffril et al., 2010). According to Possenriede & Plantenga, (2011), satisfaction arises when they are happy with what they have done and that indirectly boost their work performance to do the best for their work.

Employee performance is when the employee is happy and satisfied with their work that they will perform up to the ultimate satisfaction. If the employees are happy with their job, they will perform better in doing their work. Based on the previous study, Koopmans et al., (2012) have come out with questionnaires to measure how well the employee is performing, this is to show that how crucial is the employee performance towards an organization. Employee performance (EP) is being measured based on the standard set by the organisation (Hameed & Amjad, 2009). However, it also can be looked at the behaviour (Beauregard & Henry, 2009) of the employees.

Based on that notion, the researcher proposed that there is a significant relationship between Flexible Working Arrangement and Employee Performance.

FLEXIBLE WORK ARRANGEMENTS (FWAs)

Flexible work arrangements (FWAs) is the third variable in this study. Having FWAs as third variable will make the employee's performance even greater than before, because when employees are having job satisfaction, indirectly they have performed towards achieving the organisational goals (Beauregard & Henry, 2009). Thus, FWAs is nothing new to big giant companies like Google. They believe that having such flexible work arrangements (FWAs) will make them perform better and successfully implement it at their workplace.

According to Shagvaliyeva & Yazdanifard, (2014), they believe that the employees can produce a better result and perform up to their best of standard towards the organisational goals. They also believe that by promoting flexible work arrangements, they can have their work-life balanced, increased employee wellbeing and reduced stress level at the workplace (Shagvaliyeva & Yazdanifard, 2014).

However, according to Chen, (2015), he said that having flexible work arrangements will increased employees job satisfaction and organisational commitment. Thus, conferring to the 2012 National Study of Employers (Matos & Galinsky, 2012), most companies implemented FWAs to permit their employees to be able to manage their work hours and places. For example, 77 per cent of companies specified that they have obtainable flexible work time, and 63 per cent reported flexible workplace. It will also reduce absenteeism and tardiness, enhance workers morale, enhance basic physical fitness, production increase, increase savings, be competitive in the market, and profit-making opportunities.

Based on that notion, the researcher proposed that there is a significant relationship between Flexible Working Arrangement and Job Satisfaction.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

- a) H1: There is a significant relationship between Job Satisfaction and Flexible Working Arrangement.
- b) H2: There is a significant relationship between Flexible Working Arrangement and Employee Performance.
- c) H3: There is a significant relationship between Flexible Working Arrangement and Job Satisfaction.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The overall population for academicians in several private universities in Klang Valley, Malaysia is 24,276 academicians from 53 private universities (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2014). Out of 24,276 academicians throughout Malaysian population, this study focused only on several private universities in Klang Valley that practice flexible work arrangement (FWAs) as one of many ways to achieve their quality of life in an organisation. Four universities have been identified based on the four criteria as stated, 1) practice flexible working arrangements (FWAs), 2) offer distance learning program, 3) online teaching and assessment and 4) academicians are above one hundred. Thus, based on those criteria, the total academicians' populations from four universities are approximately 500 academicians. According to Krejcie & Morgan (1970), the actual population for four selected private universities is only 500 academicians that leads to the sample size of 220 academicians. The four private universities have been identified for data collections.

A two-stage cluster sampling has been chosen for this study. The first stage of cluster sampling has been determined earlier by dividing the targeted population into four groups (Scheaffer, Mendenhall, & Ott, 2009). The reasons why this two-stage sampling was chosen is because it is fast, relatively inexpensive or less costly economic efficiency compared to probability sampling (Miller, Johnston, Dunn, Fry, & Degenhardt, 2010). The targeted respondents in this study were the professors, associate professors, senior lecturers, and lecturers.

The second stage of cluster sampling was to select fifty-five (55) of lecturers and above from each university to be given the questionnaires to be distributed. A decision on the study can be made based on 100 to 220 sampling or respondents. Due to that reason, 220 respondents have been given the survey questionnaire to be answered. Given the time frame of two weeks for the respondents to answer and return the feedback was appropriate and enough time to do so. Since the targeted respondents were 220, the researcher adds another 50 instruments

to be distributed in order to make sure enough targeted instruments returned. Returned respondents were only 188.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework is the structure that can hold or support a theory of a research study.

Figure 1: Source: Adopt and adapted from; Spector's (1997) on the Job Satisfaction; L. Koopmans (2012) on Employee Performance & Australian Government, Workplace Gender Equality Agency on Flexible Working Arrangements (FWAs).

DATA ANALYSIS

In this study, descriptive statistics were utilised to describe the demographic profile of respondents and regression analysis for estimating the relationship among the variables. Hierarchical MLR has been used to test the relationship between the variables.

RESULTS OF ANALYSIS

In the Model Summary Table 1.1, the correlation coefficient R squared is 0.480 means 48 % of the variance in Flexible Working Arrangements is explained by the model.

Table 1.1: Model Summary table for Job Satisfaction and Flexible Working Arrangements

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.693 ^a	.480	.478	.81489	

a. Predictors: (Constant), JobSatisfaction1

b. Dependent Variable: FlexibleWorkingArrangements_1

Table 1.2: ANOVA Table for Job Satisfaction and Flexible Working Arrangements

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	114.819	1	114.819	172.910	.000 ^b
	Residual	124.175	187	0.664		
	Total	238.995	188			

a. Dependent Variable: FlexibleWorkingArrangement@C1

b. Predictors: (Constant), JobsSatisfaction@C1

From ANOVA Table 1.2, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was calculated on job satisfaction and flexible working arrangements. The analysis was significant, $F(1, 187) = 172.910$, $p = 0.000$ ($r = .693$). However, in coefficients table shows the details.

From the Coefficients Table 1.3, the p-value of the independent variable Job Satisfaction is 0.000. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 then we accept H_1 . The relationship between Job Satisfaction and Flexible Working Arrangements is significant, therefore we accept H_1 . From the Coefficients Table 1.3 under the column of Unstandardized Coefficients, Beta readings of the independent variable Job Satisfaction is -0.470 means indicates that the variable contributes -0.470 to the prediction of the dependent variable.

Table 1.3: Coefficients table for Job Satisfaction and Flexible Working Arrangements

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	11.292	.246		45.840	.000
	JobSatisfaction1	-.470	.036	-.693	-13.150	.000

a. Dependent Variable: FlexibleWorkingArrangements_1

In the Model Summary Table 1.4, the correlation coefficient R squared is 0.292. This means 29.20% of the variance FWAs and Employee Performance is explained by the model.

Table 1.4: Model Summary table for Job Satisfaction and Flexible and Working Arrangements on Employee Performance

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.543 ^a	0.292	0.288		1.36213

a. Predictors: (Constant), FlexibleWorkingArrangement1, JobSatisfaction1

b. Dependent Variable: EmployeePerformance1

From the Coefficients Table 1.4, the p-value of the independent variable Flexible Working Arrangements is 0.000. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 then we accept H₂. The relationship between FWAs and Employee Performance is significant, hence we accept H₂. From the Coefficients Table 1.4 under the column of Unstandardized Coefficients, Beta readings of the independent variable Flexible Working Arrangement is 0.596. This indicates that the variable contributes 0.596 to the prediction of the dependent variable.

Table 1.5: ANOVA table for Job Satisfaction and Flexible Working Arrangements on Employee Performance

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	144.575	2	72.288	38.961	.000 ^b
	Residual	345.106	186	1.855		
	Total	489.681	188			

a. Dependent Variable: EmployeePerformance1

b. Predictors: (Constant), FlexibleWorkingArrangements_1, JobSatisfaction1

From ANOVA Table 1.5, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) was calculated on job satisfaction and flexible working arrangements on employee performance. The analysis was significant, $F(2, 186) = 38.961, p = 0.000 (r = .543)$. However, in coefficients table shows the details.

Table 1.6: Coefficients table for Job Satisfaction and Flexible Working Arrangement on Employee Performance

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-4.307	1.440		-2.990	.003
	JobSatisfaction1	.470	.083	.484	5.672	.000
	FlexibleWorking Arrangements_1	1.077	.122	.752	8.807	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EmployeePerformance1

In the Model Summary Table 1.6, the correlation coefficient R squared is 0.292. This means 29.2% of the variance in Employee Performance is explained by the model.

From the Coefficients Table 1.6, the p-value of the independent variable Job Satisfaction is 0.484. Since the p-value is more than 0.05 then we accept H₀. The relationship between Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance is significant, hence we accept H₃. From the Coefficients Table 1.6 under the column of Unstandardized Coefficients, Beta readings of the independent variable Job Satisfaction is .484. This indicates that the variable contributes 0.484 to the prediction of the dependent variable.

CONCLUSION

As for the conclusion from this study, the result showed that H1, H2 and H3 were accepted as all the result were significant. Job satisfaction towards flexible working arrangement (FWAs) was significant between Job Satisfaction. While for FWAs towards employee performance was also significant and last but not least, JS and EP was also significant. These were supported by (Chen, 2015), that FWAs will increase JS and EP. At the same time will increase the motivation of the employees to work harder in increasing the overall performance of an organization.

Therefore, given the employees, FWAs will increase their efficiency, performance that is correlated with self-confident impact on the quality of work, loyalty to the organization and having a job satisfaction (Pruchno et al., 2000).

Such satisfaction enhances staff morale and increases loyalty, increases self-belonging towards an organization and longer-term employee performance (Scandura & Lankau, 1997). This is supported by Glass & Finley (2002), Baughman, DiNardi, & Holtz-Eakin (2003), Holzer & Kim (2005) flexible working arrangements will generate future cost-saving that associate with turnover and human resource development. Hyman & Summers (2004), Igbaria & Guimaraes (1999), Baltes, Briggs, Huff, Wright, & Neuman (1999) said that flexible working arrangements had positively impacted employees level of job satisfaction. Flexible working arrangements at the workplace has become everyone's wishes to work at home without having to go through the hassle on the road such as heavy traffic, toll, parking and petrol. According to Ortega (2009), Lee & Devoe (2012) having FWAs will definitely help the employees to increase their work performance. It is also will reduce minor disciplines that organization has always face such as absenteeism and turnover. Thus, FWAs will also increase the profit-making opportunities to an organization. (Ortega, 2009, Lee & Devoe, 2012). Therefore, given the employees FWAs will improve their performance that is associated with self-confident and impacted on their quality of work and make the employee loyalty to the organization. (Pruchno et al., 2000).

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection and analysis and writing and revising the manuscript.

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